

Formation Constants of some J-Acid Azo Dyes Metal Chelates

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The formation constants of trivalent Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Yb and divalent UO₂ ion chelates with some J-acid azo dyes have been determined pH-metrically using the Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The dissociation constants of the ligands and stability constants of the metal chelates have been determined at 25° and ionic strength of 0.1 M (NaCl) in aqueous medium. Formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 chelates has been evidenced by conductometric studies and the values of the stability constants have been explained in terms of ionisation potential, ionic radius, atomic number, electronegativity of the metal ions as well as the basicity of the ligands.

Metal chelates of azo dyes have been used as dyes¹ and indicators². Recently, J-acid azo dyes have been used as

where, x = Cl (a), Br (b), F (c), NO₂ (d), OCH₃ (e), N(CH₃)₂ (f), OH (g), COOH (h), AsO(OH)₂ (i), o-OH (j)

chromophoric reagent in the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. The present work aims to study the chelation affinity of lanthanide ions with some new J-acid (1-hydroxy-6-aminonaphthalene-3-sulphonic acid) azo dyes (1a-j) prepared by coupling J-acid with diazotised substituted anilines in acid medium³, having the general structural formula.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants of the ligands (1a-j) were calculated from the pH-metric titration curves of HCl in presence and absence of the ligands and the pK_a values are obtained directly from the formation curves and also by the average value method⁴. The results (Table 1) indicate the presence of two pK_a values for ligands 1a-f, three pK_a values for 1g, h and j and four pK_a values for ligand 1i, which is in accordance with the number of the dissociable groups present in the molecule.

The respective mixtures c (1a-j) were titrated against NaOH. A drop in pH was noticed in the metal titration curves with respect to the ligand titration curve, indicating the

TABLE I—IONISATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS (1a-j)*

Ligand	1st Method				2nd Method				Mean pK				-ΔG° kcal, mol ⁻¹ **			
	pK(̄n _A =3.5)	pK(̄n _A =2.5)	pK(̄n _A =1.5)	pK(̄n _A =0.5)	pK(̄n _A =3.5)	pK(̄n _A =2.5)	pK(̄n _A =1.5)	pK(̄n _A =0.5)	̄n _A =3.5	̄n _A =2.5	̄n _A =1.5	̄n _A =0.5	̄n _A =3.5	̄n _A =2.5	̄n _A =1.5	̄n _A =0.5
1a	—	—	4.70	10.47	—	—	4.90	10.42	—	—	4.80	10.44	—	—	6.59	14.33
1b	—	—	4.50	11.30	—	—	4.60	11.28	—	—	4.55	11.29	—	—	6.24	15.49
1c	—	—	4.80	11.25	—	—	4.78	11.20	—	—	4.79	11.22	—	—	6.57	15.40
1d	—	—	8.78	12.20	—	—	8.70	12.22	—	—	8.74	12.21	—	—	11.99	16.76
1e	—	—	9.48	11.41	—	—	9.30	11.40	—	—	9.39	11.41	—	—	12.89	15.66
1f	—	—	5.40	10.26	—	—	5.24	10.20	—	—	5.32	11.23	—	—	7.30	15.41
1g	—	9.55	10.62	11.51	—	9.55	10.65	11.50	—	9.55	10.64	11.51	—	13.11	14.60	15.80
1h	—	8.20	10.40	11.38	—	8.20	10.18	11.25	—	8.20	10.29	11.32	—	11.26	14.12	15.54
1i	2.50	4.13	8.81	12.08	2.60	4.21	8.80	12.08	2.55	4.17	8.81	12.08	3.50	5.72	12.13	16.63
1j	—	4.80	9.97	11.24	—	4.80	9.93	11.22	—	4.80	9.95	11.23	—	6.59	13.66	15.41

*1st method: Proton-ligand formation curve method; 2nd method: $\log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$, $\log (\bar{n}_A - 1) / (2 - \bar{n}_A)$, $\log (\bar{n}_A - 2) / (3 - \bar{n}_A)$, $\log (\bar{n}_A - 3) / (4 - \bar{n}_A)$ versus pH method.

**ΔG° values are calculated at 25°.

TABLE 2—MEAN VALUES OF FORMATION CONSTANTS

M ³⁺	1a	1b	1c	1d	1e	1f	1g	1h	1i	1j
log β ₁										
Sc	10.31	12.33	11.34	11.33	13.50	11.07	11.80	12.21	8.93	10.74
Y	6.53	7.43	9.25	8.56	8.62	9.30	9.13	9.02	8.97	8.33
La	9.65	12.69	10.72	7.53	9.21	7.04	7.45	7.54	10.64	8.20
Ce	10.74	8.72	8.48	8.84	9.45	7.55	7.94	8.67	8.41	8.41
Pr	10.18	12.17	9.54	7.55	9.21	9.06	11.15	9.73	10.76	8.17
Sm	10.52	11.63	10.38	7.33	9.16	10.01	9.83	8.40	10.20	8.17
Eu	8.78	12.75	10.37	8.59	9.39	10.01	10.74	9.63	11.17	9.22
Gd	10.77	12.84	10.54	9.10	8.98	10.09	12.08	10.25	11.34	7.51
Tb	10.42	9.79	10.11	8.51	9.05	9.90	11.54	9.76	11.10	9.31
Dy	11.17	12.92	9.68	11.38	9.12	10.39	11.18	9.11	11.25	8.32
Ho	9.00	11.69	8.78	8.70	10.52	10.27	11.69	8.32	11.15	8.34
Yb	8.38	11.77	10.54	8.03	10.30	10.18	11.01	8.18	11.21	8.39
UO ₂ ²⁺	8.38	11.77	10.54	8.03	10.3	10.18	11.01	8.18	11.21	8.39
log β ₂										
Sc	19.73	24.44	22.72	22.69	25.69	22.09	23.40	23.25	17.17	21.45
Y	12.56	12.93	17.49	16.94	16.39	17.05	15.52	16.13	16.27	15.61
La	15.18	25.07	20.08	14.13	17.13	12.67	13.03	13.88	18.18	14.21
Ce	20.56	17.74	16.33	17.15	18.18	13.38	12.56	15.59	12.93	14.59
Pr	17.84	23.63	18.17	14.62	17.24	17.12	20.23	16.88	18.77	14.51
Sm	18.50	21.16	19.87	13.75	17.12	18.34	17.57	15.80	17.30	15.64
Eu	16.92	25.83	20.28	16.66	18.07	18.19	19.40	18.31	19.07	17.50
Gd	20.31	25.69	20.02	17.40	17.29	20.00	20.87	18.88	21.03	14.91
Tb	19.03	18.97	18.47	16.46	17.31	18.06	20.50	17.35	22.20	17.58
Dy	21.03	25.43	18.33	19.99	17.56	19.31	20.09	17.01	19.14	15.83
Ho	16.83	21.41	16.57	17.43	19.22	19.28	18.51	14.68	19.75	16.22
Yb	15.56	22.25	19.21	16.21	19.88	19.30	19.68	15.21	19.89	15.82
UO ₂ ²⁺	15.39	24.09	20.36	18.51	18.05	18.80	16.70	16.73	16.31	17.41
log β ₃										
Sc	28.55	35.55	33.55	33.56	—	32.23	34.16	33.95	24.80	31.51
Y	18.21	—	25.23	24.50	21.95	23.68	20.94	21.88	21.88	21.14
La	19.62	36.83	27.04	20.55	23.93	18.55	—	17.65	23.90	18.54
Ce	29.50	26.27	22.54	23.42	24.54	18.43	—	21.20	17.20	19.66
Pr	24.30	30.94	26.25	20.41	24.20	24.00	27.68	23.70	24.25	18.89
Sm	25.23	30.19	27.88	20.25	23.12	26.35	23.67	21.52	23.78	20.30
Eu	23.94	37.83	29.10	24.30	25.60	25.95	26.61	25.94	25.90	25.55
Gd	27.72	37.32	28.14	25.30	24.83	28.18	28.88	26.94	27.75	20.76
Tb	27.15	27.28	26.40	23.96	25.67	26.08	27.57	25.49	31.37	25.37
Dy	28.17	37.37	26.20	28.68	24.79	28.46	27.98	25.05	26.65	22.30
Ho	22.99	30.23	24.27	25.93	26.92	27.85	26.31	19.51	26.15	22.80
Yb	22.67	32.25	27.80	23.71	28.65	27.90	26.78	20.06	27.48	21.62
UO ₂ ²⁺	20.52	35.13	29.25	26.41	23.92	26.58	21.49	22.15	22.43	22.78

release of protons due to chelate formation. The mean values of the stepwise formation constants, log β₁, log β₂ and log β₃ for the chelates of the trivalent Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Yb and divalent UO₂ with the mentioned ligands (Table 2) were calculated utilising the equations given by Sarin and Munshi⁴. It is apparent from the data that 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (M : L) complexes are formed. The relation between the ionisation constant pK_a and the stability constants log β₁, log β₂ and log β₃ was studied. It is apparent from Fig. 1 that there is good linear correlations for pK₁ vs log β₁. When log β₂ or log β₃ was

plotted vs ΣpK_a, no correlation was obtained due to structural reasons.

The stabilities of the lanthanide-1 complexes were studied as a function of ionisation potential, ionic radius, atomic number and electronegativity of the metal ions. It was found that log β values of most of the formed chelates exhibit the trend commonly found in many lanthanide complexes⁵. The formation constant increases among lighter lanthanides and then falls at Eu, Gd or Dy (what is known as gadolinium break), after which the value increases again for the heavier lanthanides with increasing

Fig. 1. Relation between the stability of the complexes $\log \beta_1$ and the basicity of the ligands pK_1 .

atomic number and decreasing ionic radii. However, there is no linear increase of $\log \beta_1$'s with increase of the chemical potential (z^2/r). This may be attributed to steric effects or increasing the coordination number of the metal ion greater than six. Increasing electronegativity increases the stability constants of the chelates up to Eu after which it

decrease to Gd and Ho, then the stability increases again in the series of heavier lanthanides.

The conductometric titration curves for the complexes show three breaks at molar ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (metal ion : ligand) which is in accordance with the results obtained from the pH-metric titrations.

Experimental

The substituted arylazo J-acid dyes (1) were prepared by coupling the corresponding diazotised amines with J-acid in acid medium and the resulting dyes were crystallised from the appropriate organic solvent several times till constant m.p. was obtained. Standard solutions of 0.1 M HCl, 0.2 M NaOH and 1.0 M NaCl were prepared. Stock solutions of dye (0.001 M), lanthanide perchlorate (0.01 M) except of Y^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} , were prepared and standardised⁶. The solutions of desired strengths were obtained by the subsequent dilution. Y^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} solutions (0.1 M) were prepared from their nitrate salts:

Three mixtures of the following constituents were prepared : (a) 3 cm³ 0.1 M HCl + 5 cm³ 1 M NaCl + 42 cm³ water, (b) 3 cm³ 0.1 M HCl + 5 cm³ 1 M NaCl + 20 cm³ 10⁻³ ligand solution + 22 cm³ water, (c) 3 cm³ 0.1 M HCl + 5 cm³ 1 M NaCl + 20 cm³ 10⁻³ ligand solution + 5 cm³ 10⁻³ M metal perchlorate solution + 17 cm³ water. The mixtures were titrated pH-metrically against 0.2023 M NaOH using a Lseibold, G-103, pH-meter (Austria) at 25°. The average number of protons associated with the ligand (n_A) at different pH-values, the average number of ligands attached to a metal ion (n) and the free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated using the standard equations^{4,7}. The methods used for calculating the stability constants were, interpolation at half n values, correction term, successive approximation and mid-point methods⁷. All calculations were carried out using a programmable 7200 Casio calculator.

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